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there's
something
science
can do.

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[Merck signs the longest renewable energy deal in Asia-Pacific](#): On November 5, Merck announced a 20-year power-purchase contract with SK Innovation E&S to add 16 megawatts of renewable electricity for its Life Science sites in Daejeon and Songdo, South Korea. Starting in late 2027, the deal will supply 75 percent of the electricity for these sites, moving Merck closer to its 2030 target of sourcing 80 percent of its purchased electricity from renewables.

[Eli Lilly expands AI-driven drug discovery](#): On November 10, Lilly signed a research deal worth over US\$100 million with Insilico Medicine to use its Pharma.AI platform for designing new therapeutic candidates. The agreement builds on Lilly's recent AI investments, including its collaboration with Nvidia to create a pharmaceutical supercomputer and the rollout of the TuneLab platform, which gives biotech companies access to Lilly's AI models.

[Pfizer wins \\$10 billion bidding war for Metsera as Novo Nordisk exits](#): Pfizer closed a \$10B acquisition of pharmaceutical startup Metsera, allowing the company to enter the rapidly growing weight-loss drug market following the [April discontinuance](#) of its in-house GLP-1 treatments in April 2025. Metsera has several GLP-1 drugs in various phases of development. The deal comes after [Novo Nordisk also attempted](#) to acquire Metsera in October for \$6.5B, forcing Pfizer to increase its offer.

[National Institute of Health \(NIH\) grant cuts disrupt clinical trials](#): A [JAMA Internal Medicine study](#) published on November 17 reported that NIH grant terminations between February and April 2025 under the second Trump administration disrupted 383 clinical trials involving more than 74,000 patients. The cuts hit infectious-disease studies, international research and preventive or behavioural-medicine trials hardest.